

SUSTAINABILITY, ENVIRONMENTAL, AND SAFETY ASPECTS IN THE PRODUCTION OF BIOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Future product design requires sustainable processes and may with great benefit partially be based on composites made from agricultural by-products. The EU project Biocomp addressed the manufacturing and the parallel assessment of the world wide sustainability of such an approach as well as the environmental and safety issues for each of the life cycle phases.

Keywords: Sustainable development, environmental safety, green products

INTRODUCTION

Future product design requires sustainable processes and eco-innovation in material development, e.g. biocomposites completely made from natural resources. Common products made from composites have environmental benefits due to their low weight, good mechanical properties and resistance to corrosion. Similar benefits are found for the biocomposites made of natural fibres and matrix materials. As such benefits are well recognized, the understanding of other environmental and social implications concerning the manufacturing and use of biocomposites are still rather poor. These implications are “*Issues affecting the industry include health and safety, the emission of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), energy consumption and toxicity from manufacture.*” [1]. Thus, both environmental and social impacts concerned with occupational health and industrial safety needs to be considered. The tools provided by the well known methodologies “Live Cycle Assessment” and “Risk Assessment” are appropriate measures to assess these environmental and societal impacts.

The future more sustainable product design was the main concept of the EU project “New Classes of Engineering Composite Materials from Renewable Resources” (Biocomp – NMP2-CT-2005-515769). The consortium consisted of research institutes, SME’s and universities from 11 European countries, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Italy, Poland, Spain, Romania, Sweden and United Kingdom. The Biocomp objective was to use by-products from agriculture, wood, paper pulp industries such as lignin, polylactide, starch, furan resins, woven and non-woven fibres and fibre mats to obtain innovations on engineering thermoplastic and

thermosetting materials to find new model products. The RTD included the path from raw materials to final top quality, high tech engineering composite materials and model products and a parallel socio technological assessment of the contributions of the material and energy streams leading to these model products. In general the live cycle for bio materials leading to the biocomposites may be divided into different phases as shown in table 1. The paper will address the important findings made regarding the world wide sustainability of the bio materials used, as well as the environmental and safety aspects of the processes leading to the final products.

This investigation is based on life cycle analyses found in the literature and /or investigations that have been performed by the project partners. The main investigations found for hemp/flax agriculture and yarn production are references [2;3] reporting the results of the former EU project HEMP-SYS project contract no. QLK5-CT-2002-01363, results on the PLA manufacturing are found in [4;5] and the very recent LCA on the furans and lignin are found in [6]. The assessments are using standard environmental impact classification factors [7;8], e.g. Acidification, Ecotoxicity, Human toxicity, Eutrophication/Nitrification, Climate change, Depletion of abiotic/biotic resources, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Photo-oxidant formation. The overall objective of the evaluation is to assess the new materials and to show how they will fulfil specific ecological and economic criteria including safety and occupational health aspects.

Table 1 Generic live cycle phases for bio materials

Agricultural phase:	Growing of specific plants for the fibres and the matrix materials. The possible application of fertilizers, pesticides and other important “auxiliaries” as petrol for the machinery needed.
Pre-processing phase:	The preparation of the different types of fibres and the processing of the raw materials for the matrix components as e.g. the flax, hemp and wood fibres on one side and the furan resins, crops oils and starch components for the matrix on the other side. This may involve the assessment of larger scale industrial processes applied.
Processing phase:	This phase concerns the preparation of the bio composites and the application of different types of additives needed. The additives (as flame retardants, colours etc.) that are found important due to quantity or adverse effects of some precursors may also be evaluated in former phase.
Consumption phase:	Usage of bio composites by costumers and spread of the products into society. This phase is not applicable within this study as the usage and life time of the new products are not known.

Waste treatment phase:	Aspects of re-use, recycling, biodegradability and incineration are being analysed in this phase including the waste streams from each production step.
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COMPOSITE MATERIALS PRODUCED AND APPLIED

Biocomposites are similar to the traditional composites made out of two components bound together using different technologies. The fibres (e.g. hemp or flax) give the strength (especially when the fibres are aligned in one or two dimensions). The other component is working as a matrix and glues the fibres together. The resins used in bio materials can be polylactic acid, polyfuranylalcohol, plantoils, lignin and others. The manufacturing of biocomposites using extruders, moulding or other processes will within each process include several processing stages. Each stage need different inputs, like energy, material and water resources to operate and each stage will have some outputs, like emissions to air, to land and to water. The prototype products manufactured within the BIOCAMP project are not being optimized due to the lowest energy consumption within all process steps and therefore a confident balance of the optimal energy needs cannot be made. In general the same processing conditions may be applied for both the biocomposites and the traditional composites. This indicates that the processing of biocomposites may be not more energy consuming than the common products. In other cases the biocomposites may use less energy as the processing conditions will run at lower temperatures [9].

PRODUCTION AND APPLICATION OF BIO RESINS

Poly Lactic acid (PLA)

Lactic acid is both produced by chemical synthesis and fermentation processes. For the latter the carbohydrates are coming from a variety of sugars e.g. from sucrose found in sugar beets, sugar cane or dextrose from corn. Since about 1995 all new production capacities for lactic acid employ the fermentation process. It provides high purity L-lactic acid needed for the polymerisation to PLA [10]. The carbohydrates are converted into lactic acid using homolactic organisms *Lactobacillus* at elevated temperatures under anaerobic conditions. Nutrients are required and can be added e.g. in form of yeast extract and corn steep liquor. The fermentation is a batch process requiring about 4 to 6 days and the yields of the calcium lactate is about 90% w/w based on the glucose content of the carbohydrate source. The presently best achievable yield is above 90 % with a product concentration of 90g/l calcium lactate. [11].

Some decades ago, lactic acid has been mainly synthetically produced by hydrolysis of lactonitrile [10]. Main producers were Musashino Japan and Sterling Chemicals USA. Lactonitril is synthesized from ethanal and hydrogen cyanide, which again are made from crude oil and natural gas. Hydrogen cyanide [12] is mainly produced reacting methane with ammonia and oxygen in the Andrussov process at about 1200 °C over a platinum catalyst [13;14]. Ammonia is produced in large quantities reacting nitrogen (air distillation e.g. Linde process) and hydrogen (e.g. steam reforming) at high pressure and temperature.

Figure 1 Fossil fuel energy consumption for PLA production using a variety of technological options [4]: 1) established process as described in text, 2) process improved using gene manipulated organisms active at low pH, 3) PLA using the whole plant, and 4) same as 3), but using wind power for electricity

The non-renewable energy requirements for the different variation of PLA production using the fermentation path are shown in Figure 1. The production paths can be optimized to reduce the consumption of fossil fuel based energy by different means. The fermentation process is improved by genetic modified microorganisms active at very low pH values and technologies that utilize the whole crops instead of the fruit (corn) to provide the sugar. The latter will also decrease the land use needed to grow e.g. corn crops and by that may minor the competition of corn as food, energy or material purposes. Further the application of renewable energies reduces the need of fossil fuels to produce PLA. The overall energy and material amounts based on fossil fuel are lowest for PLA as seen in Figure 2. Nevertheless, the pure process energy demands (fossil fuel usage) for PLA is higher compared to a number of the conventional polymers listed as e.g. PolyPropylene. Therefore, this is a clear indication that technological improvements to process PLA are necessary to reduce the gross energy demand below the demand for common polymers to make PLA production truly sustainable.

Furan

The raw materials to produce furan based materials are completely based on agricultural waste products containing pentosan, as e.g. corncobs, bagasse, flax shives, residues of olive extraction, and rice hulls. The pentose content (% dry mass) [15] for these residues ranges range between 30-32, 25-27, 23, 21-23, and 16-18, respectively. Commercially, furfural is produced through acid-catalysed digestion of the pentosan, which is the only commercial route [16]. Furfural is the precursor for all molecules in that family (furyl, furfuryl, furoyl, or furfurylidene radicals in the chemical industry.

Figure 2 Comparison of fossil fuel energy used in various polymers [4]:

PC=polycarbonate; HIPS=high impact polystyrene; GPPS=general purpose polystyrene; LDPE=low density polyethylene; PET SSP=polyethylene terephthalate, solid state polymerisation (bottle grade); PP=polypropylene; PET AM=polyethylene terephthalate, amorphous (fibers and film grade); PLA=poly lactide (first generation); PLA B/WP (poly lactide, biomass/wind power scenario).

Furfural is produced mainly from corncobs and bagasse in large quantities of more than 280000 tonnes per year mainly in China with 200000 tonnes per year [17]. The worldwide production capacity is slightly higher than the consumption [18]. The first commercial production of furfural was started by the Quakers Oats Company in 1922 using an agricultural waste product oat hulls. The same company also made furfuryl alcohol commercially available through a high pressure reduction of furfural. From the 1960s to now the foundry industry became a major consumer of resins manufactured from furfural and furfuryl alcohol. There are a number of continuous and batch processes [15] as the batch process by Quaker Oats and the batch process used in China, which are well established, simple and inexpensive batch processes. The Agrifurane or Petrole Chimie process consist of several batch reactors in series, while there are developed continuous processes by Quaker Oats, by Escher Wyss and by Rosenlew. More modern processes are the suprathern process by Krupp and the SupraYield process [19]. These processes are rather old and not the most effective processes with regard to yield, energy efficiency and emissions. In Table 1 the Chinese Batch process is compared with a new concept “Supra Yield”. It is seen that an investment in technology would improve the cost and sustainable manufacturing of furfural very much.

Lignin

Lignin may be considered as a natural polymer and is a major component of many plants. It is one of the most abundant organic polymers and is usually processed from wood. Beside from wood lignin can also be processed using Sarkanda grass, which is a grass growing in South Asia and may be up to 3 m height. The grass can be harvested and be processed in a pulp factory. The so called black liquor is a waste product from pulping industries and from there lignin may be extracted. The necessary inputs are electricity, water, steam, compressed air and auxiliary

chemicals. After the pulping process the black liquor is treated in the lignin precipitation system to separate the lignin and after drying pulp-lignin is produced as output. The residues from the lignin precipitation system are burned providing an energy source.

Table 1 Comparison of key parameters for the Chinese Batch process and the new SupraYield technology [19]

Parameter	<u>Chinese Batch</u> Process	<u>SupraYield</u>
Yield %	35	~80
Batch time (h)	5	1
Added acid (%)	4	2
Pressure (atm)	6	18
Steam use (t/t)	60	10
Effluent (kg COD/t)	1000	50

Another lignin source is found in the ethanol conversion process, as lignin is a waste product in the bio-ethanol processing. For every 1 kg of produced bio-ethanol 0.66 kg lignin may be extracted. Here the same issues as for furan need to be considered as revealed by the analysis made by [6]. The global warming potential for producing lignin is much lower compared to some common polymers. The important improvements recommended in the report for an even better sustainable production is the following. The energy supply and consumption is of importance as the utilization of biomass is an important contributor to the overall LCA results. The source of raw materials, auxiliary chemicals and transport are important issues that have a potential for improvements. In an internal report Fraunhofer ICT [20] evaluated the lifecycle of a flax/lignin composite material to be used for watches. The comparison with ABS material revealed a better performance of the flax /lignin composites not only on the greenhouse potential, but also for the other impact categories as ODP, acidification potential, eutrophication and photochemical oxidant potential. The important factor found is the utilization of less fossil fuel based energy for the bio composite.

PRODUCTION AND APPLICATION OF NATURAL FIBRES

Hemp and flax agriculture consists of the following steps: soil preparation, sowing, drilling, and treatment with fertilizers /pesticides. This is followed by harvesting, drying and the retting process. Hemp and flax are not new agricultural crops used in Europe, but has been used for textiles and other purposes up to about the end of world war II. Due to several technological and political reasons hemp was replaced by other fibres. Recent recovery and subsequent research found that hemp agriculture is beneficial [21;22] for several reasons, as e.g. high fibre yields, little requirements for or no pesticides, hemp crops suppresses weed growth, hemp crops suppresses some major soil borne diseases, hemp is easily incorporated into cropping systems and it is commonly grown in rotation with winter wheat, less herbicides needed also for wheat as hemp suppresses weeds, hemp leaves the soil in very good conditions, and successive growth of wheat after hemp increases the yields of wheat harvesting [2;3].

For Flax the following is found: Flax follows a cereal crop frequently wheat in the crop rotation, Soil structure requirements similar to hemp, Fertilisation depends on actual soil (for good quality fibres nitrogen fertilisation should not be given in excess), Produces fibres and seed (sawing, oil extraction, animal feed), Yields vary from year to year, Harvested by pulling machine, but without desiccation (no Glyphosate), Susceptible to competition by weeds in early growth phase ->weed control , Requires pesticides (herbicides for weed control, sowing seeds treated with fungicides) [2] ^(page 31).

Dissanayake et.al.[8] found that the pre-manufacturing (decortications, hackling, carding and spinning) only are assumed to have no effect or low effect for all the standard environmental impact categories. The same is valid for the flax seeds separation by the rippling process. For all steps/processes the ozone depletion potential, the photochemical oxidants creating potential, as well noise and vibrations and odour was as well found no effect or low effect categories. Turunen et.al [2;3] made in 2006 a life cycle analysis of hemp and flax to be used in textile production. This was part of the EU project HEMP-SYS [2]. Within this study they developed a generic Central-European crop production scenario mainly based on the hemp production in Hungary and supported by the French experiences. They also conclude that the amounts of fertiliser and fuel do not seem to vary significantly across Europe. In their LCA the investigation starts with ploughing of the field (26-32 cm deep). Amount of fertilizer applied are: 68 kg N, 30 kg P₂O₅ and 114 kg K₂O per hectare and amount of fertilizer calculated due to the needs of the plants according to good agricultural practice. Two passes by the tractor are required to spread the fertilisers: 1) for spreading the nitrogen and one for the P₂O₅/K₂O. The Seedbed is harrowed and 55kg/ha seed is sown. The seed is produced assuming similar inputs as the agriculture of the fibre crops, but with the exception that the amount of seed is only 25kg/ha, giving a seed yield of 1000 kg/ha and the need for mechanical weed control. No pesticides are used for the agriculture of hemp in the European generic scenario. Nevertheless, in Italy there is a newer “Baby Hemp” technology approaching that uses a herbicide. Here the growth of the hemp is stopped when the length is about 120 -140 cm using the herbicide Glyphosate in combination with the auxiliary substance ammonium sulphate (4 kg /ha of each). The seeding is using 100 kg seed per hectare and the amount of fertilisation is being adjusted to match the stem yields. The stem yield for normal hemp is assumed to be 8 t/ha measured as dry stems containing 14% humidity.

SAFETY ASPECTS

Activities in agriculture to produce the raw materials and the processing to refine them involve operations that need considerations in terms of occupational health and industrial safety. These are concerned with the operation of machinery as e.g. cutting devices and the application of pesticides in the agricultural phase. The (pre-) processing uses chemical industrial and biotechnological processes. Here the safety aspects are concerned with the handling of toxic substances, process parameters as high temperature and high pressure, ignition, fires, explosions and possible run-away reactions.

The manufacturing of PLA (synthesis and fermentation) and of polyfurfuryl alcohol applies a number of hazardous substances that are highly flammable and (highly) toxic as e.g. ethanol and hydrogen cyanide for the synthesis of PLA and corrosive acids are applied as hydrochloric acid (toxic gas) and sulphuric acid. Both are to be treated with care to avoid occupational health problems. While lactic acid and its polymer are of no concern regarding health effects, the use of furfural and furfuryl alcohol impose some safety and health issues as these are both highly

flammable and in contact with strong acids may react explosive. Furfural is also carcinogenic and the inhalation of furfural vapours cause severe irritation of the eyes and nose. It is found on experiments with rats that a single exposure to vapours up to a concentration of 126 ppm was fully tolerated. Higher exposure results in dose dependent mortality leading to 100% deaths >221 ppm and an LC_{50} = 189 ppm. Repeated exposure of rats to 40 ppm furfural for 1 h/day, 5 days/week, for 7, 15, and 30 days did not cause any deaths [23].

It is found that especially in the old fashioned synthesis process of LA some toxic and highly flammable substances have been used. Here it may be concluded that the substitution with the fermentation process will avoid the adverse effects to human and the environment and possible major industrial hazards due to accidents e.g. from fire hazards and explosions within a wider distance to the installation. Such scenarios are not possible for the batch fermentation process, though these are not without possible hazards and e.g. the likelihood of the spread of gene manipulated bacteria need to be assessed more detailed to provide the full picture of the safety benefits.

SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS OF THE PRODUCTION OF BIOCOMPOSITES

Biomass demand in the energy sector and the manufacturing industry give rise to sustainability issues on e.g. protection of soil and water resources, nature conservation and social equity. The following is more detailed discussed in [24]. Biomass production for food and non-food uses may become competing land uses. Thus the cases of sustainability evaluation of increased cultivation of e.g. hemp and flax fibres for biocomposites have at least two important aspects: “What is the competing land use?” and “What is the alternative fibre product or plastic substitute for the composite?” The outcome of a sustainable evaluation will be influenced if the annual crops hemp and flax are grown on cultivated land and they would compete with other food crops. Or corn would be used either as food, energy or material crop. Both hemp and flax are old culture plants with multiple uses for oils, medicine and fibres. The environmental performance of these plants compared to other crops will therefore also depend on their suitability to meet multifunctional goals. In the assessment of the fibres for industrial purposes the relative sustainability will depend on the reference product that would substitute the natural fibre, e.g. is the reference product to the natural fibres hemp or flax a wood fibre or a fossil fuel based fibre? In a situation of increasing use of biomass the demand of land use is a scarce resource and the planning will depend on the natural fibres that are grown. Here the flexibility of annual crops versus perennial crops or afforestation for wood production speaks in favour of annual crops since the land use can quickly be changed back to food crops. This is particularly true when the future food demands are unknown and the annual crop fibres are irreplaceable by other natural products. However, if afforestation is part of a multifunctional landscape planning it can be favoured over annual fibre crops due to topics concerning water protection, recreational uses etc. In conclusion the use of fibres from old cultural plants such as hemp and flax cannot be valued as sustainable or unsustainable per se and depends strongly on the situation within certain regions and countries.

The biological limit of a biomass based economy is the total marine and terrestrial biomass production fuelled by solar irradiation. The current global annual net primary production is estimated to 104.9 Pg carbon per year equally distributed in marine and terrestrial environments [7]. To which extent this resource can be expanded or utilised further without compromising ecological balances and specific nature conservation goals in global “high conservation value

areas” is unknown. The current nature conservation issues are used as evidence for a direct link between non-food use of agricultural products, and loss of valuable habitats in natural ecosystems. The human appropriation of net primary production (HANPP), e.g. the share consumed by humans in the biomass decomposition and mineralisation steps of the carbon cycle is estimated to 15-25% [8]. This share is considerably higher in densely populated areas of the planet. The cultivation of crops that are exclusively intended for non-food industrial uses may raise the issue of food security and land use in general. The world population of undernourished individuals was of 864 million in 2002-2004 of which 88% lived in the Least Developed Countries [6]. However, this is seen as a symptom of lack of livelihood and social exclusion rather than a general global food supply problem. The World Wildlife Foundation stresses that current use of renewable natural resources exceeds resource renewal rates. Based on the ‘ecological footprint’ (EF) accounting system developed by [12], and adopted by the World Wildlife Foundation, current renewable and non-renewable resource use is calculated in global hectares of average productive agricultural land. According to these calculations, each global citizen currently runs an annual deficit of 0.4 global hectares [15].

CONCLUSIONS

The comprehensive study of the literature and the input from the partners revealed the sustainable potential of the biomaterials used for composite manufacturing. The main impact seems to be within the agricultural and pre-processing phases of the different components of the composites. The manufacturing of the biocomposites is assumed to be comparable to the processing of the common composites with a tendency to e.g. less energy usage for the biocomposites. In the overall evaluation it is necessary to include social issues as occupational health and industrial safety considerations, especially in cases where different technologies are available to be able to determine the best solution. The question of sustainability is not to be answered generally, but depend on the specific framework for agriculture in a region.

Recent research [25] showed that the agriculture for e.g. hemp fibres has a number of benefits as it e.g. improves the soil that is also beneficial for the follow up crops, e.g. less herbicides needed. The normal growth of hemp uses no pesticides by default, but flax need some regular treatments. In the literature data on GF processing may be found in [8;26;27] and comparing the energy for glass fibre mat production and a flax fibre fibrous web as shown in Table 2 reveals an about 5 times decreased energy consumption for the flax fibre containing material.

Table 2 Comparison on the energy demands for glass fiber mat and flaxfiber fibrous web production [27]

Glassfiber-mat	Energy demand (MJ/ kg)	Flaxfiber fibrous web	Energy demand (MJ/ kg)
Raw materials	1,7	Seed production	0,05
Mixture	1,0	Fertilizer	1,0
Transport	1,6	Transport	0,9
Melt	21,5	Agriculture	2,0
Fiber manufacturing	5,9	Decortication	2,7

Glassfiber-mat	Energy demand (MJ/ kg)	Flaxfiber fibrous web	Energy demand (MJ/ kg)
Mat line	23	Fibrous web production	2,9
Total:	54,7		9,55

The matrix materials furanyl alcohol and lignin are produced from agricultural or process waste products. Therefore, the usage of these will not address the resource depletion issue or be subject of the discussions on the competition between plants being used as food or materials. In contrast the present PLA production is e.g. using corn and therefore a balance between plants for food and energy-/material has to be drawn. New developments though will enable to produce PLA using whole plants. Crops especially in the US are gene manipulated and grown using pesticides (round-up).

The industrial procedures to convert biomass into e.g. furfural are often rather old fashioned and a great potential for improvements on yield and clean production is recognized, as it is pointed out by EMPA [6] for the furfural production, where the utilization of biomass for production of process energy is questionable. The same analysis finds that the global warming potential for producing furfuryl alcohol is much lower compared to some common polymers. The source of raw materials, auxiliary chemicals and transport are other important issues that have a potential for improvements. For the furfural production a number of newer and more effective technologies are available or under development as shown in Table 1. The introduction of cleaner technology should be prioritized in the future. Biocomposites can be used in advanced designs and are a promising alternative for more sustainable products.

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REFERENCES

1. Anderson J, Jansz A, Steele K, Thistlethwaite P, Bishop G, Black A; green guide to composites; 1-36. 2004. Garston , Watford WD25 9XX, BRE and NetComposites.
2. Turunen L, van der Werf HMG; Life Cycle Analysis of Hemp Textile Yarn; 1-80. 2006. HEMP-SYS project contract no. QLK5-CT-2002-01363.
3. Werf HMGvd, Turunen L. The environmental impacts of the production of hemp and flax textile yarn. *Industrial Crops and Products* 2008; 27(1):1-10.
4. Vink ETH, Rabago KR, Glassner DA, Gruber PR. Applications of life cycle assessment to NatureWorks(TM) polylactide (PLA) production. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 2003; 80(3):403-419.
5. Azapagic A. *Polymers, the Environment and Sustainable Development*. John Wiley & Sons; 2003.
6. EMPA; LCA overview of furan and lignin based ecobinders; D1.15, 1-43. 2008.
7. Comparison of environmental impact categories. 2008.

8. Comparative life cycle assessment for natural vs. glass fibres as reinforcements for composites: part 1 - literature review. International sustainable materials, polymers and composites conference; 2007.
9. Eisenreich N; private communications (Fraunhofer ICT, Pfinztal). 2009.
10. Chahal S, Starr JN; Lactic Acid; web edition, 1-8. 2006. Weinheim, Wiley - VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA. Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry.
11. Clark JH, Hardy JJE. Towards sustainable chemical manufacturing: polylactic acid - a sustainable polymer? In: Azapagic A, Perdan S, Clift R, editors. Sustainable development in practice: Case studies for engineers and scientists. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.; 2004. p. 250-282.
12. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hydrogen_cyanide#Production_and_synthesis. 2009.
13. Andrussov L. The catalytic oxidation of ammonia-methane-mixtures to hydrogen cyanide. *Angewandte Chemie* 1935; 48:593-595.
14. Andrussov L. catalytic oxidation of ammonia-methane mixtures to hydrogen cyanide. *Ber* 1927; 60:2005.
15. Zeitsch KJ. The chemistry and technology of furfural and its many by-products. 1 ed. Elsevier; 2000.
16. Hoydonckx HE, van Rhijn WM, De Vos DE, Jacobs PA. Furfural and Derivatives. Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry. 2008 ed. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co KGaA; 2007. p. 1-29.
17. Win DT. Furfural - Gold from Garbage. *AU J T* 2005; 8(4):185-190.
18. Sangarunlert W, Piumsomboon P, Ngamprasertsith S. Furfural production by acid hydrolysis and supercritical carbon dioxide extraction from rice husk. *Korean Journal of Chemical Engineering* 2007; 24(6):936-941.
19. A novel process for furfural production. South African Chemical Engineering Congress 3-5th September 2003; Sun City, South Africa: 2003.
20. Kupfer T, Wolf M-A; Erprobung der ZeroEmission Methodik am Beispiel eines Armbanduhrgehäuses aus flachsfaserverstärktem Lignin-Compound. 2000. Fraunhofer Institut Chemische Technologie; Universität Stuttgart, Institut für Kunststoffprüfung und Kunststoffkunde. Vorlaufforschung Fraunhofer-ICT.
21. Werf HMGvd, MATHUSSEN EWJM, HAVERKORT AJ. The potential of hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) for sustainable fibre production: a crop physiological appraisal. *Annals of Applied Biology* 1996; 129(1):109-123.
22. Werf HMGvd. *Emphytica* 2004; 140:13-23.
23. Gupta GD, Misra A, Agarwal DK. Inhalation toxicity of furfural vapours: an assessment of biochemical response in rat lungs. *Journal of applied toxicology* 1991; 11(5):343-347.
24. Markert F, Callesen I, Radwanski M; LCA/LCI of Biocomp Materials; D4.14 (confidential). 2008. Biocomp WP4.
25. Struik PC, Amaducci S, Bullard MJ, Stutterheim NC, Venturi G, Cromack HTH. Agronomy of fibre hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) in Europe. *Industrial Crops and Products* 2000; 11(2-3):107-118.
26. Corbiere-Nicollier T, Gfeller Laban B, Lundquist L, Leterrier Y, Manson J-AE, Jolliet O. Life cycle assessment of biofibres replacing glass fibres as reinforcement in plastics. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 2001; 33(4):267-287.
27. Diener J. *Die Angewandte Makromolekulare Chemie* 1999; 272:1-4.